

INGLIZ TILIDAGI TURKIZMLARDA LEKSIK-SEMANTIK ASSIMILYATSIYA
HODISASI

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Annotasiya. Maqolada ingliz tilidagi turkizmlarda leksik-semantik assimilyatsiya hodisasi haqida so'z boradi. So'zni o'zlashtirayotgan tilda leksik-semantik o'zlashtirilishi uning so'z yasashdagi faolligi, reseptor tilning so'zlariga aralashib ketishi, reseptor tilda yangi so'zning manba tildagi ma'nosi bilan hech qanday aloqasi bo'lmagan ma'noni ifodalanishining semantik strukturasi qayta o'zgarishlarni tushunamiz. Ingliz tilidagi turkiy leksik o'zlashtirmalarning o'tish jarayoni qanday kechganini o'rganish tilshunoslikdagi dolzarb masalalardan biridir. Ingliz tiliga o'zlashgan turkiy so'zlarning aksariyati uchun suffiksasiya so'z yasashning eng sarmahsul usuli ekanligi tadqiqotimiz davomida o'z isbotini topdi.

Kalit so'zlar: leksik-semantik assimilyatsiya, so'z yasashdagi faollik, reseptor til, leksik o'zlashtirmalar, suffiksasiya, substrat hodisasi, superstrat hodisasi.

Аннотация. В статье рассматривается феномен лексико-семантической ассимиляции в англоязычных тюркизмах. Мы понимаем лексико-семантическое усвоение слова в языке, в котором оно усваивается, его активность в словообразовании, смешивание с словами рецепторного языка, повторные изменения в семантической структуре выражения значения, которое не имеет никакого отношения к значению нового слова в языке-источнике в рецепторном языке. Изучение того, как происходил процесс перехода тюркских лексических заимствований в английский язык, является одним из актуальных вопросов в лингвистике. В ходе нашего исследования было доказано, что для большинства тюркских слов, заимствованных в английский язык, суффиксация является самым продуктивным способом словообразования.

Ключевые слова: лексико-семантическая ассимиляция, активность в словообразовании, рецепторный язык, лексические заимствования, суффиксация, феномен субстрата, феномен суперстрата.

Annotation. The article discusses the phenomenon of lexico-semantic assimilation in English Turkic words. Lexical-semantic assimilation of a word in the borrowing language is understood as its activity in word formation, its mixing with the words of the receptor language, changes in the semantic structure of the expression of the meaning of a new word in the receptor language, which has no connection with the meaning of the source language. The study of the transition process of Turkic lexical borrowings in English is one of the pressing issues in linguistics. In the course of our research, it was proven that for most Turkic words borrowed into the English language, suffixation is the most productive way of word formation.

Key words: lexico-semantic assimilation, activity in word formation, receptor language, lexical borrowings, suffixation, substrate phenomenon, superstrate phenomenon.

Kirish. So'zni o'zlashtirayotgan tilda leksik-semantik o'zlashtirilishi deganda uning so'z yasashdagi faolligi, reseptor tilning so'zlariga aralashib ketishi, reseptor tilda yangi so'zning manba tildagi ma'nosi bilan hech qanday aloqasi bo'lmagan ma'noni ifodalanishining semantik strukturasi qayta o'zgarishlarni tushunamiz. Ingliz tilidagi turkiy leksik o'zlashtirmalarning o'tish jarayoni qanday kechganini o'rganish tilshunoslikdagi dolzarb masalalardan biridir. Ingliz tiliga o'zlashgan turkiy so'zlarning aksariyati uchun suffiksasiya so'z yasashning eng sarmahsul usuli ekanligi tadqiqotimiz

davomida o‘z isbotini topdi. Suffiks yordamida so‘z yasash ingliz tilida uzoq vaqtlardan beri o‘z ahamiyatini yo‘qotmagan usullardan biridir.

Adabiyotlar tahlili va metodlar. “Til aloqasi” atamasining keng talqini O.Yespersen [1], B.A.Serebrennikov [2], Y.O.Jluktenko[3,124], YE.V.Opelbaum [4,703], A.M.Rot[5] va boshqalarning ishlarida ham uchraydi.

Misol uchun, B.A.Serebrennikov “til aloqasi”ning til substrati tushunchasi bilan aloqasi sifatida tadqiq qiladi. Substrat yoki superstrat hodisalariga N.Shayxislamov ikki tilning o‘zaro chatishuvi natijasida mag‘lub elementlarning g‘olib til strukturasiidagi belgilari mazkur tushunchani ifodalaydi, deb qaraydi. Substrat tushunchasi keng etnik aralashuv va ikki tillilik orqali mahalliy xalq tilining kelgindilar tiliga singib ketishidir.

Natijalar va muhokama. Ingliz tilidagi **-ness** suffiksi o‘zlashgan turkiy so‘zlarga yangi so‘z yasashda eng ko‘p qo‘llaniluvchi mahsuldor suffikslardan biri bo‘lib, u asosan turkiy sifat o‘zaklarga qo‘shilib mavhum ot yasashga xizmat qiladi:

turkishness: “*But they treated his ideas with respect and began under his influence, to develop in themselves a new sense of Turkishness*”. (Lord Kinross. Ataturk. London, 1959. – P. 56)

Shuningdek, **-yed** ham eng sermahsul va ko‘p qo‘llaniluvchi sifat yasovchi qo‘shimchadir. **-ed** suffiksi ot o‘zaklarga qo‘shilib “in‘om qilingan yoki ajralib turadigan” ma‘noli sifatarni yasashda xizmat qiladi. Hozirgi ingliz tilida o‘zlashtirilgan turkiy o‘zaklardan ko‘p darajada **-ed** suffiksli sifatlar yasalgan: *fezzed, yashmaked, shagreened, sequinned, divanned, caftaned, minareted, calpacked, turbaned* va boshqalar.

Turbaned: “*The procession was swelled, and by group of theological students and white-turbaned hodjaz who harangued the-men and influenced their stocato cries of “We want the shariat! We want the holy Law!”* (Lord Kinross. Ataturk, L., 1959. – P. 13).

Shuni alohida aytish kerak-ki, biz tahlilga tortgan F.Barnabining “A ride to Khiva: travels and adventures in central Asia”[6] nomli asarida **-ness, -yed** suffiksi turkiy so‘zlarga qo‘shilgan holatlarga duch kelmadik.

-an suffiksi o‘zlashtirilgan turkiy o‘zaklarga qo‘shilib sifat so‘z turkumiga oid so‘zlarni hosil qilish uchun xizmat qiladi: *Turkistan, Caspian, Khivan, sultanian, timarian, seljukian, cossackian, ottomanian* va b. Inglizcha tilidagi **-u** suffiksi (*bosh-boshy*) yordamida ham sifatlar yasalgan, masalan:

If this is done, we shall no longer hear from the authorities at St. Petersburg that they are unable to restrain their generals in Turkistan.

(Burnaby F. A Ride to Khiva. – R. 15) “*There was no dancing, only boshy games and a conjuror.*

(F.Anstey. Vice Versa. London, 1882. Vol. IV)

Ingliz tilidagi lotincha **-ate** ot yasovchi qo‘shimcha turkiy so‘zlarga qo‘shilib mavhum ot yasagan: *khanate*. Mazkur so‘z F.Barnabi asarida 37 marta qo‘llanilganligi o‘tkazilgan statistik tahlillarda o‘z aksini topdi.

It is not generally known that the first attack on this Central Asian khanate was made by the subjects of the Tzar. (Burnaby F. A Ride to Khiva. – R. 248)

Ingliz tiliga o‘zlashgan turkizmlarda ot so‘z turkumini yasovchi eng sermahsul suffikslar asosan mavhum va jamlovchi ot yasovchi suffikslar sanaladi:

-dom: vassaldom, pashadom, beydom, Turkdom va boshqalar:

The khanate was reduced to a state of complete vassaldom.

(Burnaby F. A Ride to Khiva. – R. 262)

“If such things could happen in the capital, it may be convinced that the course of justice did not run very smooth in the distant pashadoms.”

(Mac Farlane. Turkey and Its Destiny. L., 1850, Vol. I. – P. 84)

-ship: Bekship, bashawship, cadiship, Beyship va h.k.

There they reduced to their own rule the Bekships of Urgut, Faraf, Macha, Kshtut, and Maghian. (Burnaby F. A Ride to Khiva. – R. 388)

“Every Sunday and Tuesday, at the royal seraglio, where he hears cadiship and decedes in all affairs”. (Ch. Perry. View of the Levant. – P. 33)

O‘zlashtirilgan turkiy o‘zaklardan “ta’limot, maslak, shuningdek ijtimoiy tuzum, insonning fe’l-atvorini xarakterlovchi xususiyat yoki ish- harakat tarzi” ma’nosini ifodalovchi **-ism** suffiksli mavhum ma’nodagi yasama otlar paydo bo‘lgan: **Khaurism, Turkism, Tansimatism, Bashawism, Vampirism, Kemalism, Ataturkism, Pan-Islamism** va boshqalar.

... on the shores of the Bay of Khaurism, under the pretext of commercial objects, ... (Burnaby F. A Ride to Khiva. – R. 253)

So‘zlarning bu turkumi asosan publisistikada ko‘p qo‘llanilgan. **-ism** suffiksli otlar, eng avvalo, turli yo‘nalishlar va ta’limotlarda qo‘llaniluvchi so‘zlar ma’nosini ifodalagan:

“The ideological message now preached to it was symbolized by the “six arrows” of what came to be called “Kemalism”, with the addition in 1931 of statism and Revolutionism, to the four previous principles of Rationalism, Secularism, Republikanism and Popularism”.

(Lord Kinross. Ataturk. New York, 1965. - P. 518) *“In Central Asia Pan-Turanianism and Pan-Islamism do not conflict with each other”. (E.G.Mears. Modern Turkey. N.Y., 1924. – P. 512)*

“Pan-islamism, with Enver Pasha as the leading personality, was a movement with an organization under the young Turkish party.”

(Halide Edib. Conflict of East and West in Turkey. Lahore, 1935. – P. 101)

“But as time went on it came to seem an impractical dream and Ziya modified his ideas to a form of Pan-Turkism embracing only the turks within the Empire itself”. (Lord Kinross. Ataturk. N.Y., 1965. – P. 56)

Turkiy o‘zlashmalarga ingliz tilidagi –**ist** suffiksi qo‘shilgan ot turkumiga oid so‘zlar ham ko‘p miqdorni tashkil qiladi. Bularga *ataturkist, sultanist, kemalist, tanzimatist, pan-turkist* kabi so‘zlar kiradi.

Qoida bo‘yicha –**ist** suffiksi yordamida hosil qilingan otlar ham turli yo‘nalishlar va ta’limotlarning tarafdorlarini bildiradi:

“*The Kemalists, as the successors of the Young Turks were called, have pronounced judgement on nearly all the deeds of their predecessors.*” (Halid Edib. Conflict of East and West in Turkey Lahore. 1935. – P. 54)

“*With few exceptions they are reniversity graduates and convinced Ataturkists, secularists and positurists*”. (Nuri Eren. Turkey Today – and Tomorrow. London, 1963. – P. 171)

“*The Tanzimatists were the second Ottoman team, which conciously stated to re-create the state.*” (Halide Edib. Conflict of East and West in Turkey. Lahore, 1935. – P. 67)

- **ia** suffiksi ma’lum joyni ifodalashda qo‘llanilgan:

“*Hassan Kuli, Gomush Tepe, and the localities thereabouts, are now Turkomania...*” (Burnaby F. A Ride to Khiva. – R. 251)

Shunday qilib, ingliz tiliga o‘zlashgan turkizmlarning butun bir qismi grammatik assimilyatsiga uchrab, ingliz tili grammatik vositalari bilan aloqaga kirisha boshlaganligi alohida ahamiyat kasb etadi. Biz tahlil qilayotgan material shuni ko‘rsatdi-ki, juda ko‘p turkizmlar tilda mavjud bo‘lgan so‘z yasash modellari bo‘yicha yangi so‘zlarni hosil qilish imkoniyatini qo‘lga kiritadi va ingliz tilida so‘z yasalishining eng sermahsul usullari suffiksasiya, so‘z qo‘shish va konversiya hisoblanadi.

O‘zlashtirilgan turkizmlar o‘zlashtirish jarayonida yangi so‘zlarni hosil qilish uchun asos bo‘lib xizmat qilgan: ular ayrim tub so‘zlarga birikish yo‘li bilan qo‘shma so‘zlar va so‘z birikmalarini hosil qilgan.

Ularning ingliz tili tomonidan mustahkam o‘zlashtirilganligining belgilaridan biri shuki, o‘zlashtirilgan turkizmlar tub so‘zlar bilan birgalikda birikmaning tarkibiy qismiga aylangan: *khivan town, khivan’s appetite, Bokhara territory, turkoman, kirghis appetit, turkey-cock, sherbet-seller, coffee-disease, Divan-day, Turks-cap lilly* va boshqalar.

Ko‘plab turkizmlar inglizcha so‘zlar bilan oson birikib qo‘shma so‘zlar hosil qilib gibrid so‘zga aylandi va qo‘shma so‘zning har ikki komponenti bitta tushuncha ifodaladi. Ingliz so‘zlari bilan turkizmlarning erkin birika olishi alohida xususiyat kasb etadi va so‘z o‘zlashtirilganining yorqin isboti hisoblanadi. Masalan:

Now at Khiva there was always the prospect of a war with the Turkomans.

(Burnaby F. A Ride to Khiva. – R. 181) “*It was curious to talk over all these things about the war, walking again*

with a friend in the cemetery, among thousands of clustered turban-stones and gigantic cypress-trees.” (Lady Hornby. Constantinople, L., 1863. – P.167).

“*Young minds used to enter these confraternities and acquire status ranging from timar-holding to grand vizierate according to their talents.*” (Z.Gökalp. Turkish Nationalism and Western Civilization. New York, 1959. - P. 92)

Ba’zi bir turkizmlardan gibrid soʻzlarning koʻp sonli miqdori hosil qilingan. Misol uchun, NED lugʻati boʻyicha “**coffee**” soʻzidan 53 ta gibrid hosilalar qayd qilingan: *coffee-room, coffee-shop, coffee-pot, coffee-head, coffee-cream, coffee-corn, coffee-man, coffee-disease* va boshqalar. “**Coffee**” asosli gibrid soʻzlarning koʻpchiligi, asosan, konkret tushunchalarni ifodalaydi:

“*The coffee-houses are, perhaps, the most characteristic feature of Stamboul streets during the nights of Ramazan.*” (A.D. Duight. Constantinople Old and New. New York, 1915. - P. 268)

“*One day a Turk, passing our coffee-shop was attracted by the commotion at the door.*” (A.D. Duight. – P. 533)

Biroq qoʻshma soʻzning birinchi komponenti “**coffee**” soʻzidan yasalgan ba’zi bir gibrid hosilalar har doim ham aniq tushunchalar ifodalagan. Ayrim oʻrinlarda ular mavhum tushunchalar ham ifodalagan. Ularga quyidagi soʻzlar kiradi: *coffee-disease, coffee-habit, coffee-service, coffee-talk* va h.k.

“*There is, it is true, a coffee-habit, whose abuse is no less demoralizing than that of any other drug.*” (A.D. Duight. – P. 25)

“**Turkoman**” soʻzi F.Barnabining «A Ride to Khiva» asarida 145 marta qoʻllanilgan boʻlib, undan 38 marta sodda qoʻshma, 101 marta qoʻshma yasama, 6 marta “**Turko man**” koʻrinishida ajratilgan holdagi strukturada ishlatilgan. Qoʻshma yasama koʻrinishida asosan koʻplik formasini yasovchi –s, va qaratqich kelishigi ni yasovchi ‘s qoʻshimchalarini olgan. Masalan:

A regulation revolver, with about twenty cartridges, made up my defensive arsenal in the event of an attack from the Turkomans. (– P. 14)

The fact is, that if the Kirghiz carry off a Turkoman's cattle, no one hears of it. (– P. 248)

Qolaversa, gibrid qoʻshma soʻzlar artikl bilan ham qoʻllanilgan. Yuqoridagi misolga eʼtibor bersak, artikl millat tushunchasini ifodalovchi “**Turkoman**” soʻzi oldida qoʻllanilmoqda.

“**Turban, tulip, turkey**” soʻzlari bilan inglizcha soʻzlar birikib bir nechta gibrid qoʻshma soʻzlarni hosil qilgan.

Masalan: *turban-shell, turban-stone; tulip-fire, tulip-mozaick, tulip-wood; turkey-bird, turkey-blue, turkey-hen* va boshqalar.

Struktur tarkibi nuqtai nazaridan qoʻshma gibrid soʻzlarni quyidagi turlarga ajratish mumkin:

- 1) ikkita ot oʻzakli gibrid qoʻshma soʻz: *divan-day, turkey-bird, tulip-fire;*
- 2) ot va sifat oʻzakdan tashkil topgan: *turkey-blue, coffee-brown, coffee-royal;*

3) qo'shma so'zning birinchi qismi ot, ikkinchisi **-er** suffiksi bilan hosil qilingan boshqa ot o'zaginging birikuvidan yasalgan: *soffee-maker, sherbet-seller, Turkey-Cucler*;

4) qo'shma so'zining birinchi komponenti ot va ikkinchisi **-ed** suffiksini olgan sifatdan tashkil topgan: *coffee-coloured*;

5) har ikki qism tub sifatdan va ikkinchi qism otga **-ed** suffiksini qo'shish orqali yasalgan hosila sifat birikuvidan paydo bo'lgan gibrid qo'shma so'zlar: *white-turbaned, greyen-turbaned*.

Qo'shma gibrid so'zlarning yozilishi turlicha, ya'ni qo'shib, alohida- alohida va defis orqali yoziladi: *tulipomania, coffee cooler, sherbet-seller*.

O'zlashtirma so'zlar ingliz tilining ayrim so'zlari bilan aloqaga kirishib faqat qo'shma so'zlarni emas, balki so'z birikmalarini ham hosil qilgan. Misol uchun "ottoman" so'zi "empire, regime, sultan" va boshqa so'zlar bilan birikmalarda uchraydi.

Xulosa. Turkizmlarni leksik-semantik jihatdan tahlil qilish quyidagilarni aniqlashga imkon berdi:

a) o'zlashtirma turkizmlarning yetarli darajadagi katta miqdori ingliz tilida yasama qo'shma so'zlar va so'z birikmalarini hosil qilish uchun asos bo'lib xizmat qildi;

b) o'zining semantik strukturasi saqlab qolgan o'zlashtirma turkizmlar, hamda semantik strukturasi torayishi kuzatilgan turkizmlarning o'zlashtirilishi ingliz tili sohiblari uchun ular bildiradigan predmetlar yoki hodisalar qanchalik darajada dolzarbligiga to'g'ridan-to'g'ri bog'liqlikda o'ladi;

v) ma'nosini umumiyalashtirish va ko'chma ma'noda qo'llash orqali semantik strukturasi kengaytirgan turkizmlarni ingliz tili tomonidan o'zlashtirilgan deb hisoblash mumkin.

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